

OP9. GRAPHENE/LIPID NANOSYSTEMS FOR CANCER IMAGING AND TREATMENT

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Keywords: *Graphene, Doxorubicin, Nanocarrier, Cancer, Theranostics.*

ABSTRACT

Cancer remains a prominent cause of death, with estimates pointing to a 77% increase in the number of new cancer cases between 2022 and 2050. Present chemotherapeutic agents can induce toxicity, even at therapeutic doses, and become ineffective by multidrug resistance (MDR) development. Doxorubicin (DOX), a powerful chemotherapeutic, kills fast-growing cancer cells, but also displays toxicity in healthy tissues. Commercial DOX formulations have the disadvantage of increasing DOX aggregation and MDR. Aggregates are less effective in DNA intercalation, decreasing DOX therapeutic efficacy.

In-house made nanographene oxide (NGO) or commercial graphene oxide quantum dots (GQD) were conjugated with DOX (GQD/NGO@DOX) and inserted in nonlamellar lipid carriers to improve biodistribution. GQD possess photoluminescence providing a bio tracking tool for DOX release. DOX release is pH-triggered at the acidic pH of cancer cells. Therefore, this work aspires to enhance DOX therapeutic effect, selectivity, and pH-triggered drug release profile, allowing to trace drug delivery through imaging.

NGO were synthesized and together with commercial GQD were thoroughly characterized. GQD/NGO@DOX cytotoxicity was evaluated in L929 reference cell line and in zebrafish embryos (*Danio rerio*) through fish acute embryotoxicity (FET) assay according with the OECD test guideline (TG) 236, drawing the toxicological profile of these new conjugates. This strategy allowed the identification of the conjugates that show better performance in relation to free DOX and simultaneously allow for theranostic applications.

Current cancer treatment strategies present major drawbacks, some of which can be circumvented by our new pH-triggered nano-delivery systems, raising opportunity to tackle the ever-increasing cancer numbers.